

SCAPHO-LUNATE DISSOCIATION ASSOCIATED TO A DISTAL RADIUS FRACTURE

“The real question that remains is whether or not one should treat the dissociation along with the distal radius fracture.” *Prof. J. Jupiter*

Report of a case treated according to MGH suggested protocol:

Alejandro Lasa, Jesse Jupiter [January 2020](#)

Fractured wrist

Contralateral wrist

Incidence and Functional Outcomes of Scapholunate Diastases Associated Distal Radius Fractures: A 2-Year Follow-Up Scapholunate Dissociation.”

The Open Orthopaedics Journal, Bentham Open, 31 Jan. 2018

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KEY FINDINGS:

- Distal radius fractures are not associated with a high incidence of clinically significant scapholunate diastasis.
- When scapholunate diastasis is detected, the opposite wrist is likely to show a similar finding, so bilateral imaging is important.
- Patients with unilateral scapholunate diastase's do not need scapholunate ligament reconstruction at initial presentation.

- 2018 case.
- 54 years old, right-handed hand worker.
- Patient reports neither pain nor functional limitations before the accident.
- Right wrist trauma.

2018 case | 54 years old, right-handed hand worker | Right wrist trauma

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SURGICAL SIDE

When scapholunate diastasis is detected, the opposite may show a similar finding, so bilateral imaging is important.

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SURGICAL SIDE

CONTRALATERAL SIDE

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1 week
 X-ray
 control

"While much has been written about carpal instabilities associated with fractures of the distal radius, we still do not fully understand the significance of the radiographic picture of a wide scapho-lunate interval.

This case demonstrates the basic need to X-ray the opposite wrist as part of the preoperative planning.

The real question that remains is whether or not one should pursue the X-ray findings with intra-operative arthroscopy and treat the dissociation along with the distal radius fracture. Given the similar findings on the uninjured wrist as well as our published experience, this may not be the case. The correct approach remains in question and perhaps left to the judgement of the operating surgeon"

*Jesse B Jupiter MD
 January 2020*

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